

Interaction of Ethylacetoacetate and Phenylhydrazine Hydrochloride with 1-Hydroxy-Naphthylstyryl-2-Ketones and 1-Hydroxy-4-Bromo-Naphthylstyryl-2-Ketones and of Hydroxylamine Hydrochloride with-1-Hydroxy-4-Bromo-Naphthylstyryl-2-Ketones.

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Manuscript received 24 March 1972; revised 12 February 1973; accepted 5 July 1973

The work is the continuation of the work¹ on the interaction of these reagents with 1-hydroxy-phenylstyryl-2-ketones¹ with a view to studying the effect of the substitution of phenyl nucleus by naphthyl¹ one.

VARIOUS chalkones prepared from 2-acetyl-1-naphthol and 2-acetyl-4-bromo-1-naphthol and various aromatic aldehydes, when reacted with ethylacetoacetate resulted in the synthesis of ethyl-2-(substituted)-phenyl-4-(1'-hydroxy)naphthyl-(2')- Δ^4 -cyclohexene-6-one-1-carboxylates and ethyl-2-(substituted)-phenyl-4-(1'-hydroxy-4'-bromo)-naphthyl-(2')- Δ^4 -cyclohexene-6-one-1-carboxylates respectively. These on alkaline hydrolysis gave the corresponding cyclohexene-one derivatives.

When reacted with phenylhydrazine hydrochloride in presence of hydrated sodium acetate these styryl ketones gave, the pyrazoline derivatives.

2-Methoxy-, 4-methoxy-, 4-benzyloxy-3:4-dioxy-methylene-, 3:4-dimethoxystyryl-1'-hydroxynaphthyl-2'-ketones and 2-methoxy-, 2-methoxy-5-bromo-, 4-methoxy-, 4-benzyloxy-, 3:4-dimethoxy-, 3:4-dioxymethylene- and 3:4-dioxymethylene-6-bromo, styryl-1'-hydroxy-4'-bromo-naphthyl-2'-ketones are worked out in the above reactions.

Interaction of hydroxylamine hydrochloride in presence of sodium hydroxide in alcoholic solution was successful only in the case of simple chalkone and 4-methoxy-chalkone resulting in the synthesis of 5-aryl-3-(1'-hydroxy-4'-bromo)-naphthyl-(2')-iso-oxazolines.

Experimental

The requisite chalkone (1 g.) was taken in dry ethanol (20 ml.) and metallic sodium (0.1 g.) and ethylacetoacetate (1 ml.) were added to it. More ethanol (15 ml.) was added and mixture was refluxed on a water bath for about six to seven hours.

The reaction mixture was cooled diluted with water and acidified with hydrochloric acid. The product obtained was crystallised from a suitable solvent. The compounds from the chalkones from 2-acetyl-1-naphthol are described in Table 1 and those from 2-acetyl-4-bromo-1-naphthol are described in Table 2.

TABLE 1—ETHYL-2-SUBSTITUTED PHENYL-4-(1'-HYDROXY)-NAPHTHYL-(2')- Δ^4 -CYCLOHEXENE-6-ONE-1-CARBOXYLATE

No.	Substituent (R)	M.p.	Formula	%Found	%Required
1.	R = 2'-OCH ₃	157°-8°	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ O ₅	C, 74.85 H, 5.37	C, 75.00 H, 5.76
2.	R = 4'-OCH ₃	171°-2°	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ O ₅	C, 75.35 H, 5.47	C, 75.00 H, 5.76
3.	R = 4'-OCH ₂ C ₆ H ₅	179°-80°	C ₃₂ H ₂₈ O ₅	C, 78.40 H, 5.41	C, 78.04 H, 5.69
4.	R = 3':4' 	187°-8°	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ O ₆	C, 72.66 H, 5.41	C, 72.55 H, 5.12
5.	R = 3':4'-(OCH ₃) ₂	172°-3°	C ₂₇ H ₂₆ O ₆	C, 72.33 H, 5.59	C, 72.64 H, 5.83

TABLE 2—ETHYL-2-(SUBSTITUTED)-PHENYL-4-(1'-HYDROXY-4'-BROMO)-NAPHTHYL-(2'- Δ^4 -CYCLOHEXENE-6-ONE-1-CARBOXYLATE

No.	Substituent	Crystallised from	Colour and shape	M.p.	Formula	%Found	%Required
1.	R = H	Dilute alcohol	Yellow needles	177°-8°	C ₂₆ H ₂₁ BrO ₄	C, 64.28 H, 4.69 Br, 16.82	C, 64.51 H, 4.51 Br, 17.20
2.	R = 2'-OCH ₃	Alcohol	Yellow needles	190°-1°	C ₂₆ H ₂₃ BrO ₅	Br, 16.28	Br, 16.16
3.	R = 2'-OCH ₃ -5''-Br	Acetic acid	Yellowish brown needles	216°-17°	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ Br ₂ O ₅	Br, 27.49	Br, 27.87
4.	R = -4'-OCH ₃	Alcohol	Yellow shining needles	172°-73°	C ₂₆ H ₂₃ BrO ₅	C, 63.35 H, 4.98 Br, 15.88	C, 63.05 H, 4.64 Br, 16.16
5.	R = -4'-CH ₂ C ₆ H ₅	Alcohol	Yellow shining needles.	173°-74°	C ₃₂ H ₂₇ BrO ₅	Br, 14.13	Br, 14.01
6.	R = 3'' : 4''- 	Alcohol	Yellow needles	200°	C ₂₆ H ₂₁ BrO ₆	Br, 15.53	Br, 15.71
7.	R = 3'' : 4''- 	Alcohol	Yellow shining needles	182°-83°	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ Br ₂ O ₆	Br, 27.41	Br, 27.21
8.	R = 3'' : 4''-(OCH ₃) ₂	Alcohol	Yellow shining needles.	173°	C ₂₇ H ₂₅ BrO ₆	Br, 15.03	Br, 15.23

The requisite ester (1 g.) was taken in 5% solution of sodium hydroxide (20 ml.) and ethanol (50 ml.) was added to it. The reaction mixture was refluxed on a boiling water bath for about six hours, cooled, diluted and acidified with hydrochloric acid. The solid obtained was crystallised from ethanol. The compounds from simple hydroxy series are given in Table 3 and those of bromohydroxy series are given in Table 4. 2 : 4-Dinitrophenylhydrazones derivatives prepared from compounds in Table 3 are given in Table 5.

Phenylhydrazine hydrochloride (1 g.) and sodium acetate (1.6 g.) were dissolved in water (10 ml.) and the requisite chalkone (0.5 g.) and ethanol (50 ml.) were added to it. The mixture was refluxed on a boiling water bath for about three hours. When cold, the reaction mixture was diluted with water and the solid obtained was crystallised from a suitable solvent. The compounds of simple hydroxy series are given in Table 6 and those from bromo-hydroxy series are given in Table 7.

TABLE 3—2-(SUBSTITUTED)-PHENYL-4-(1'-HYDROXY)-NAPHTHYL-(2'- Δ^4 -CYCLOHEXONE-6-ONE

No. of ketone	No. of ester used from Table 1	Substituent	M.p.	Formula	%Found	%Required
1	1	R = 2'-OCH ₃	175°-6°	C ₂₂ H ₂₀ O ₃	C, 80.19 H, 5.68	C, 80.23 H, 5.84
2	2	R = 4'-OCH ₃	192°-3°	C ₂₃ H ₂₀ O ₃	C, 80.00 H, 5.58	C, 80.23 H, 5.84
3	3	R = 4'-OCH ₂ C ₆ H ₅	200°-01°	C ₂₈ H ₂₄ O ₃	C, 82.53 H, 5.36	C, 82.85 H, 5.71
4	4	R = 3'' : 4''- 	185°-6°	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ O ₄	C, 76.81 H, 4.82	C, 77.09 H, 5.00
5	5	R = 3'' : 4''-(OCH ₃) ₂	174°-5°	C ₂₄ H ₂₂ O ₄	C, 77.04 H, 6.18	C, 77.00 H, 5.88

TABLE 4—2-(SUBSTITUTED)-PHENYL-4-(1'-HYDROXY-4'-BROMO)-NAPHTHYL-(2')-Δ⁴-CYCLOHEXENE-6-ONE

No.	No. of ester used from Table 1	Substituent	M.p.	Colour and shape of the crystals	Formula	%Found	%Required
1	2	R = 2'-OCH ₃	195°-96°	Brown granules	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ BrO ₃	Br, 18.62	Br, 18.91
2	3	R = 2'-OCH ₃ -5'-Br'	195°-96°	Brown granules	C ₂₃ H ₁₈ Br ₂ O ₃	Br, 31.62	Br, 31.87
3	4	R = 4'-OCH ₃	180°-81°	Brown granules	C ₂₃ H ₁₉ BrO ₃	Br, 18.54	Br, 18.91
4	5	R = 4'-O-CH ₂ -C ₆ H ₅	198°-99°	Brown granules	C ₂₆ H ₂₃ BrO ₃	Br, 15.63	Br, 16.03
5	6	R = 3' : 4'- 	180°-81°	Dark brown	C ₂₃ H ₁₇ BrO ₄	C, 63.31 H, 4.00 Br, 18.02	C, 63.15 H, 3.89 Br, 18.30
6	7	R = 3' : 4'- and 6'-Br	161°-62°	Brown needles	C ₂₃ H ₁₆ Br ₂ O ₄	Br, 30.56	Br, 31.00
7	8	R = 3' : 4'-(OCH ₃) ₂	126°-27°	Greyish granules	C ₂₄ H ₂₁ BrO ₄	Br, 17.31	Br, 17.66

TABLE 5—2 : 4-DINITRO-PHENYLHYDRAZONE OF 2-(SUBSTITUTED)-PHENYL 4-(1'-HYDROXY)-NAPHTHYL-(2')-Δ⁴-CYCLOHEXENE-6-ONE

No. of Dinitro-phenyl-hydrazone	No. of ketone from Table 1	Substituent R	M.p.	Formula	%Found	Required
1	1	2'-OCH ₃	167°-8°	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₆	N, 10.36	N, 10.68
2	2	4'-OCH ₃	233°-4°	C ₂₆ H ₂₄ N ₄ O ₆	C, 66.82 H, 4.47 N, 10.37	C, 66.41 H, 4.58 N, 10.68
3	3	4'-OCH ₂ C ₆ H ₅	135°-6°	C ₃₀ H ₂₈ N ₄ O ₆	N, 9.15	N, 9.33
4	4	3' : 4'- 	232°-3°	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ N ₄ O ₇	N, 10.28	N, 10.40
5	5	3' : 4'-(OCH ₃) ₂	216°-7°	C ₃₀ H ₂₆ N ₄ O ₇	N, 9.90	N, 10.10

TABLE 6—1-PHENYL-3-(1'-HYDROXY)-NAPHTHYL-(2')-5-(SUBSTITUTED)-PHENYL-PYRAZOLINE

No. of Pyrazoline Derivative	Substituent R	m.p.	Formula	%Found	%Required	Colour and shape of crystals
1	2'-OCH ₃	178°-9°	C ₂₆ H ₂₂ N ₂ O ₂	N, 7.42	N, 7.10	Yellow needles
2	4'-OCH ₂ C ₆ H ₅	90°-91°	C ₃₂ H ₂₆ N ₂ O ₂	N, 5.62	N, 5.95	Dard red needles.
3	3' : 4'-(OCH ₃) ₂	167°-8°	C ₂₇ H ₂₄ N ₂ O ₃	N, 6.35	N, 6.63	Pale yellow

Hydroxylamine hydrochloride (5 g.) and the requisite chalcone of the bromo-hydroxy series (1 g.) were taken and sodium hydroxide solution (20 ml., 10%), water (10 ml.) and ethanol (50 ml.) were added to it. The reaction mixture was refluxed on a water

bath for about three hours. The reaction mixture was cooled, diluted with water and acidified with hydrochloric acid and the solid thus obtained was crystallised from a suitable solvent. The products are described in Table 8.

TABLE 7—1-PHENYL-3-(1'-HYDROXY-4'-BROMO)-NAPHTHYL-(2')-5-(SUBSTITUTED)-PHENYL-PYRAZOLINE

No.	Substituent	Crystallised from	Colour and shape of crystals	M.p.	Formula	%Found	%Required
1	R = H	Alcohol	Yellow needles	196°-97°	C ₂₅ H ₁₉ N ₂ BrO	Br, 17.76 N, 6.21	Br, 18.05 N, 6.32
2	R = 2'-OCH ₃	Acetic acid	Dark brown granules	148°-49°	C ₂₆ H ₂₁ N ₂ BrO ₂	Br, 16.56	Br, 16.91
3	R = 2'-OCH ₃ & 5'-Br	Acetic acid	Dirty brown granules	200°-01°	C ₂₆ H ₂₀ N ₂ Br ₂ O ₂	N, 4.87	N, 5.07
4	R = 4'-OCH ₃	Alcohol	Pale yellow granules	110°-11°	C ₂₆ H ₂₁ N ₂ BrO ₂	Br, 16.58	Br, 16.91
5	R = 3' : 4' 	Alcohol	Yellow granules	99°-100°	C ₂₆ H ₁₉ N ₂ BrO ₃	Br, 16.12	Br, 16.43
6	R = 3' : 4'-(OCH ₃) ₂	Alcohol	Pale yellow needles.	181°-82°	C ₂₇ H ₂₃ N ₂ BrO ₃	Br, 15.62	Br, 15.90

TABLE 8—5-(SUBSTITUTED)-PHENYL-3-(1'-HYDROXY-4'-BROMO)-NAPHTHYL-(2')-ISO-OXAZOLINE

No.	Substituent	Crystallised from	Colour and shape of crystals	M.p.	Formula	%Found	%Required
1	R = H	Alcohol	White needles	181°-82°	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ NBrO ₂	N, 3.62	N, 3.805
2	R = 4'-OCH ₃	Nitrobenzene	Brownish needles	232°-33°	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ NBrO ₃	N, 3.84	N, 3.52

Reference

1. S. V. Tendulkar and G. V. Jadhav, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1972, **49**, 1005.